

WORK WITH GIFTED STUDENTS IN FINE ARTS CLASSES

Baymetov Botir Boltaboyevich

Chirchik State Pedagogical University professor

Khamrakulova Mukaddam Tajikozi kizi

Doctoral student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14358679>

Annatsiya. This article discusses the development of ways to achieve effectiveness in teaching gifted students in fine arts in secondary schools and its application in the educational process.

Key words: general, secondary education, school, efficiency, unique, talent, effective, research, recommendations, special, psychological and pedagogical, tests, talent.

One of the important tasks of teachers is to find opportunities to increase their independence, initiative and responsibility in organizing the educational process, taking into account the unique characteristics of gifted students in fine arts lessons. Gifted students achieve deeper mastery of individual academic subjects or parts of them at will. They want to quickly and deeply absorb various knowledge and information and plan their learning activities. Taking this into account, the development of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms that help talented students independently seek and find answers to questions that interest them is today one of the most important tasks of every art teacher.

Talented youth are the pearl of our nation and a factor ensuring the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its worthy place in the world community. As we know, students, especially those studying in the field of arts, have a number of talents, such as artistic talent, general intellectual talent, professional talent, leadership talent, and practical talent is also considered to identify and guide them towards a specific goal. one of the important tasks in the field of education today. Therefore, identifying talented students among secondary school students and preparing them for republican and international scientific Olympiads and studying in academic lyceums, developing, on a scientific basis, improved mechanisms for processes such as the development of abilities, is one of the urgent tasks of pedagogy. became one.

In order to further increase the interest of students studying in secondary schools in fine arts classes, and at the same time increase the effectiveness of fine arts classes, it is necessary to implement the following series of activities:

- First of all, this is a scientific, theoretical and methodological justification for the fact that the pedagogical and psychological task is to determine the

abilities specific to fine arts students in secondary schools and to develop certain ways of doing this.

-Secondly, scientific research on discovering students' talents, analysis and generalization of advanced teaching experience.

-Thirdly, when determining the interests and abilities of fine arts in secondary schools, using modern didactic principles and giving examples of the rich heritage left to us by Uzbek folk masters, fine arts of students to increase their interest in lessons.

-Fourth, it is necessary to develop an aesthetic attitude by drawing images of birds and animals when depicting a landscape.

In short, on the basis of theoretical approaches and the situation in practice, work with students in fine arts lessons is improved, the assimilation of principles, the development of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms and in this regard, the study of advanced pedagogical theories used in educational institutions of developed foreign countries and their widespread use during lessons is one of the most important tasks facing a fine arts teacher today.

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